

The relative frequency of nematodes per tiller in a field in Comilla district, Bangladesh, 23 September 1978. Note: 16% of tillers were still not infested.

of the distribution (see figure). The crop is sown during the first rains, when no water stands in the fields. Nematodes have little chance of migrating from infested hills (primary infestation) to

nearby hills until the floods arrive 6 to 8 weeks later. The gap in the distribution represents the 2-month lag before secondary infestation by water-borne inocula can begin. With the advent of

floods, there is a burst of new infestation because the nematode population, although confined inside the primary infestation, has been growing. That accounts for the central mode in the population. Secondary infestation at initial flooding may cause the disease to spread over long distances. As the population continues to increase in primary and secondary infestations the nematodes spread through water, which accounts for the left-hand mode. This tertiary infestation consolidates the ufra patch.

If this Interpretation is correct, examination of the nematode population before panicle initiation will have several uses in ufra research: 1) to determine the inoculum source in experiments in farmers' fields (by presence or absence of the right-hand mode), 2) to distinguish between individual components of the nematode population growth rate, and particularly 3) to permit study of nematode population growth independently of the host's tillering behavior (by considering the rate at which the right-hand mode moves in that direction). ■

Flowering and yield response of late-maturing varieties under normal and waterlogged conditions

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Eighteen late-maturing varieties were tested under normal and waterlogged conditions (30–50 cm water depth) during 1977 kharif. The experiment was conducted in randomized blocks with 3 replications, fertilized with N, P₂O₅, and K₂O at 60-30-30 kg/ha.

Flowering was generally delayed under waterlogged conditions. The delay ranged from 1 to 11 days longer than under normal conditions (see table). Tiller number and yield were also reduced by waterlogging.

Only Panidhan 1, a selection of IR442, increased significantly in grain yield

Flowering and grain yield under normal and waterlogged conditions. Patna, India.

Designation	Parentage	Days (no.) to flowering		Yield (t/ha)	
		Normal	Water-logged	Normal	Water-logged
IET3235	IR8/SLO13	125	126	5.0	4.4
IET3236		124	126	4.3	4.0
IET3257	CR63-3218-1/Pankaj	120	121	4.7	4.3
IET3261	IR8/BJI/IR22	115	117	3.8	3.4
IET4084	IET728/CR1014	122	123	4.1	3.8
IET4086	CR36-48/CR70-80-2	108	119	4.1	3.8
IET4087	CR63-5218-1/Pankaj	115	118	3.4	2.8
IET5631	F1IR2042/CR94-13	122	124	4.5	3.8
IET5633		122	123	4.1	3.3
IET5638		114	115	4.5	3.8
IET5656	RPW6-13/Sona	117	118	4.1	3.6
IET5852	Pankaj/Jagannath	132	133	4.1	3.5
IET5853		131	133	4.9	4.3
IET5855	Sona/Mahsuri	125	126	4.4	3.8
Intan		122	125	2.6	2.4
Mahsuri		118	119	3.0	2.6
Pankaj		116	118	5.0	4.1
Panidhan-1	IR442 selection	102	104	2.0	2.3
C.D. at 5%				0.60	0.52

under waterlogging, possibly because of its intermediate plant height and ability to elongate with rising water.

IET3235, IET3257, IET5853, and

Pankaj gave the highest yields under waterlogged conditions. IET3235 and Pankaj were also the highest yielders under normal water conditions.

and Pho Kha. At harvest, Page Sampe Tuah had the most spikelets per panicle; ARC6000, the most spikelets per square meter; and Shoa-nan-tsan and ARC6000, the highest spikelet fertility.

The table, which gives the best donors from our tests, shows that many indicas are more cold tolerant than the japonicas.

The possibility of selecting early lines at Los Baños, Philippines, in the wet season, despite the high temperature, was tested by comparing the growth duration of the 219 entries in the 1978 IRCTN planted both at

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Cold tolerance

Highlights of the Korea-IRRI Collaborative Program on Rice Cold Tolerance

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A collaborative Korea-IRRI program on rice cold tolerance was initiated in late 1977. The first experiments were conducted in 1978 at Chuncheon Branch, Crop Experiment Station, Office of Rural Development. This report highlights some of the experiments.

A total of 750 entries from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN) and early generation breeding lines from Korea, Indonesia, and IRRI were subjected to continuously flowing cold water, 17 to 27°C, from the tillering stage until maturity. Varieties responded widely in tolerance. The best entries for each agronomic character follow:

Well-exserted panicles: Somewake, Oirase, Bandalbyeo, Thankote Marsi, IR5867-50-3-2-2-1, IR9202-22-3-2.

Short growth duration: Matsumae, China 1039, K140-52-3, Fuji 269, K39-96-1-1-1-2.

Intermediate plant height: Firooz, HP46, Habiganj Boro II, IR2403-PLPB-7-2-1-3B, IR4097-P1P6-1B, IR4999-B-Jn2B, IR5086-P1P6-2B, IR5467-2-2-2, IR10212-12, Jaliya, MPR-1, Paro White, Thankote Marsi.

High spikelet fertility: IR9202-32-2-3, IR8460-7-2-1, IR5868-112-1-7-1-1, IR2403-PlpB-5-4-1B, IR9202-25-1-2, China 988 (HPU16), China 988-LS 13.

Good phenotypic acceptability at maturity: IR5867-50-3-2-2-2, IR7167-33-1-7-3, IR7167-33-2-3-3, IR7167-33-2-4-1, IR7167-33-2-4-3, IR7167-33-2-5-1, IR9202-22-3-2.

To identify extremely cold-tolerant parents for the breeding program, the best Korean and IRRI selections were subjected to 17°C water from

tillering to maturity.

Naengdo 13 had excellent panicle exsertion. Fuji 269 and ARC6240 had the shortest growth duration. The tallest at flowering were Silewah, Heugdae gu.

Days (no.) to flowering at IRRI

Varieties that were excellent in at least 3 plant characters desired in low-temperature areas. Korea-IRRI collaborative program, 1978.^a

Agronomic character	ARC 6000	Leng Kwang	Stejaree 45	01 Byeo	Ggae Byeo	Shoa-Ga-Dau	Shoa-Nan-Tsan	HR 33
Good phenotypic acceptability	x	x	x	x			x	
Excellent panicle exsertion	x	x		x				
Optimum culm length		x			x	x	x	x
Earliness (days)	111	119	114	126	125	127	113	138
Stable growth duration	x			x	x	x		x
Good tillering	x	x						
Long panicles						x	x	x
High spikelet no./panicle					x			
High spikelet no./m ²	x	x	x				x	
High spikelet fertility	x	x	x	x			x	

^a x = desired characteristic is present.